

Impact of Pre and Post Joining of Self Help Groups (SHGs) on occupational status and mode of savings - A study w.r.t. Yelahanka Urban, Bengaluru

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Abstract: Purpose : The major intention of the present paper is to know how far the demographics impact on the mode of savings and occupational status of respondents before and after joining SHGs. The inclusion of women empowerment in the UN's Millennium Development Goals evidently speaks about the significance of women empowerment. The previous researches reveals that microfinance through microcredit has positively improved the well being of women clients. Women empowerment has been well recognized as a pre-requisite condition to reduce the level of poverty in developing nations (Aysha et al. 2018).

Methodology / Design : A well drawn questionnaire was managed as schedule after knowing the literacy level of women respondents. A comparative ANOVA and Kendall's co-efficient of concordance statistical tools were performed to know exactly difference between before joining and after joining SHGs. Further, chi-square and contingency co-efficient tests are also performed.

Findings : The present research work found that all the demographics are showing significant variation with high degree of relationship except occupation details which reveals not significant with low degree of relationship which arised on account of spread over equally to the stated different profession. Respondents found better mode of savings after joining SHGs where respondents insisted on parking savings in their SHGs, and totally rejected to park their savings with relatives / friends and neighbors. Further, they also rejected chit funds and cash in hand also found with small portion of respondents. The occupational details found to be better after joining SHGs where 23% of respondents involved in vegetable selling and substantial decrease in seasonal fruit selling.

Keywords: Improvements, IGAs, Savings formation, empowerment, urban poor, savings, occupation, before and after.

Introduction :

Distribution of economic gains equal to and all is assuming greater significance at present. Policy framers and economists stress on the distribution of economic gain among the poor and deserved which empowers the masses at gross root level (Dadhich, 2001, Ravi and Venkataramana, 2005; Sultan 2005; Sarangi, 2008). SHGs help in capacity building, training and participatory approach in the planning of self employment ventures. They provide a common platform for the promotion of activities in clusters and the provision of infrastructure facilities, technology (Sethi et al 2001; Borbora et al, 2021). Microfinance, serves both the unbanked and under banked and reduces poverty (John Agyekami Addae, 2015). Microfinance of late gained a high recognition as an effective tool in improving the life quality of people not only in rural areas but also in towns and slums. Microfinance as an instrument will aid development of the society and alleviate poverty (Li Gen et al. 2011). Women in the society are marginalised and faces difficulty in accessing formal credit on accounting of demanding security (Laha and Kuri, 2014; Saramathi & Mohan, 2011, Peprah, 2012). Microfinance is a type of service provided to low income people who have no access to financial services (Julia Kagni, 2005). It has been accepted as a successful model, where poor have no place in formal financial institutions (Swathi Sharma, 2018). Innumerable studies proved that microfinance is a good strategy to alleviate poverty (Kabeer 2005; Mayoux 2001, Otero 2019).

Statement of the problem

Planners so far gave significance to the rural poverty alleviation and scant attention is given to urban poverty alleviation. Like rural poor, urban poor also requires organized financial assistance towards meeting their needs like medical, education and children marriages. SHG members requires financial products. One of the biggest challenge of our country is economic women empowerment which can only be attained by making women educated, economically liberated and independent (Chetra Singh et al; 2017). The life of the poor living in urban slum without a living standard should be addressed proper. Awareness among the urban poor should be created so as to involve in income generating activities. India can properly if women are encouraged to participate in the economic activities and often the urban poor who are involved in SHG activities should be well trained. As a strategy microfinance alleviates poverty and encourages to involve in IGAs and Savings Creation.

Review of literature

Shobha and Shalini (2015) conducted a survey on the perception of women about personal financial planning in the city of Bengaluru. The study found that Indian Women give priority to family and children's requirements more than her requirements for financial needs of individualistic financial security. Further, there is a difficulty in convincing spouse and family and still it is a biggest challenge for the women to create their financial plans. The study also reveals that women still feel that gold, real estates, bank deposits, insurance products and provident funds are the most safe instruments for investing, while they felt that mutual funds, derivatives, chits, stocks and shares as riskier investment. Lack of knowledge on the part of women influence their ability to earn return for them.

A study by Suganya (2017) was conducted in Virudhunagar district of Tamil Nadu, India, to probe the influence of financial literacy through micro credit schemes on economic empowerment of Self Help Group Women members. The study used financial literacy scale and economic empowerment questionnaire which were developed and standardized by the investors. The study reveals that financial literacy like saving skills, financial knowledge, borrowing skill and investment skill, financial knowledge, borrowing skill and investment skill are playing a very critical role in economic empowerment of SHG women members. In addition to financial literacy the moderator variables also facilitating economic empowerment among the SHG members.

Hasan, M. et al. (2021) one of the opinion that financial literacy is considered as one of the vital factors of financial inclusion. The rural people's financial knowledge about financial services was studied and the researchers expressed that proper understanding of financial products is essential. The study reveals about the approaches to getting financial access i.e., banking, microfinance and Fin Tech (Mobile banking). Further the study highlights that financial literacy had a positive effect on access to finance.

Sandeep Kumar et al. (2020) expressed that financial literacy is about enlightening women investors about their financial knowledge which helps them proper knowledge to evaluate different investments. The present study showed evidence to support that there is a significant mean score difference in women's awareness level about various investment avenues based on their qualification level.

Advashnavig (2022) stated that microfinance in India plays a major role in the development of India. It was as an antipoverty vaccine for the people living in rural areas. The researcher further expressed that utmost significance of microfinance in India is that it dispenses the access to capital to the small entrepreneurs.

Objectives of the study:

1. To know the impact of demographics on occupational status and mode of savings.
2. To analyse the occupational status of respondents between pre and post joining of SHGs.
3. To study the mode of savings pre and post joining of SHGs.

Hypotheses :

1. Demographics of respondents are not impacting on the pre and post savings and occupational status.
2. There is no difference in the occupational status between pre and post joining of SHGs.

3. There is no difference in the mode of savings between pre and post joining.

Research questions :

1. What are the reasons behind demographics not impacting on the study?
2. What is the difference in mode of savings between pre and post joining period?
3. Is there any difference in occupational status between pre and post joining of SHGs.

Research Methodology

The present study used analytical methodology. In order to test the hypotheses both the primary and secondary data has been collected, compiled and analysed. The primary data collected through a well drawn questionnaire and researcher himself conducted interview with respondents in a natural setting. The secondary sources include, journals, reports, books and internet. 100 respondents were interviewed in Yelahanka Urban area and semi urban area. All SHGs members were interviewed using convenient sampling technique. The respondents belongs to Yelahanka Urban area and semi-urban area. Comparative ANOVA and Kendall's co-efficient of concordance statistical tools were performed and data was properly analyzed. In addition to the above statistical tools, Chi-square and contingency co-efficient also performed to know the significant variation and relationship between in variables.

Survey Findings

Table - 1 report about socio economic characteristics of respondents. There are 100 respondents and out of 100 respondents 85 are married, 10 single, 3 divorcee and 2 separated. 48 respondents belongs to 28-32 age group, 23 to the 33-37 years, 11 to the > 38 years, 10 to the 23-27 years and 8 to the 18-22 years. 23 are involved in vegetable selling 19 are selling seasonal fruits, 16 each petty shop and pickle / papad selling, 15 doing agriculture and 11 are tailors. Education status data reveals that there are 10 illiterates, 41 completed 10th standard, 27 PUC and 22 are bachelor degree holders. 42 respondents monthly income stood in between 10K-20K followed by 21 getting in the range of 20K-30K, 17 above 30K, 12 in between 5-10K and 8 < 5K per month. 59 are living in urban area of Yelahanka, 21 in semi urban, 12 in urban slum and 8 in urban remote area. 95 participated in social activities, 81 are trained, 14 waiting and 5 not trained. 92 are voting and supporting a candidate in election. All the characteristics of respondents are showing significant variation with high degree of relationship except occupation which implies that after joining SHG respondents involve in different occupation more or less equal number of respondents involved in different jobs.

Table - 2 & 3 divulge data on occupational status of respondents before and after joining SHGs. There were 66 respondents who expressed strongly agree over the statements followed by 18 agreed and 16 somewhat agree. Before joining SHGs, 23 were involved in seasonal fruit selling and after joining it was reduced to 19. Similarly there was also reduction in doing agriculture and before joining 21 were involved in agriculture but after joining it was reduced to 15 and similar with tailoring also. The number of vegetable sellers sharply increase from 14 to 23, and marginal increase in the number of respondents doing business of papad and pickle selling. The increase trend also seen in the case of tailoring. The F-ratio before joining was found to be 46.12. The comparative data reveals that the respondents were switched to better income giving profession. Agriculture is becoming costly and hence we find decrease in number after joining SHGs. The sharp rise in petty business is only because this profession gave better returns. There were 72 respondents who stated strongly agree followed by 18 agree and 10 somewhat agree. The F ratio after joining SHG found to be 68.75 and the difference between after and before is $68.75 - 46.12 = 22.63$, which is greater than TV 3.68 @ 5% level with $V_1 = 2$ and $V_2 = 15$ and hence ANOVA fails to accepts H_0 and accepts H_1 and it is conclude respondents involvement in IGAs found sufficient improvement.

Table - 4 & 5 reveals comparative changes in mode of savings between before and after joining SHGs. Surprisingly there were 58 respondents who deposited in their SHGs and the formation of SHGs intention is fulfilled. Before joining SHGs respondents use to park their savings with relatives friends and neighbors an unsafely mode of savings, and after joining it was reduced to only 2 on account of awareness creation in the SHGs. Similarly 32 respondents before joining behind out funds which is again on unbelievable mode and due to maximum awareness creation it was reduced to 8. The 'w' value before joining stood at 2.39 and after joining if rose to 6.4. The difference being 4.01. The chi-square statistic value stood at 84.21 after using the formula, $x^2 = K(n-1)w$. The calculated value being 84.21 with $df = 7$ and at 5% level of accuracy, 'W' fails to accept H_0 and accept H_1 and hence it is concluded that there exist significant relationship between the variables after joining SHGs and respondents are more aware of mode of savings only after joining SHGs.

Conclusion :

Financial literacy among the SHG women members is essential and hence conveniently the members should attend training programmes. An empowered women is more aware of coming out from domestic violence, voting, purchase of goods, children education, starting a new enterprise. Micro finance programmes through SHGs is one of the identified and most powerful tool of poverty and unemployment alleviation. There is strong growing concern about upliftment of urban poor who also requires financial assistance in order to lead a responsible living. Urban poor are growing with growth in Urban Yelahanka. The present research work found that all the demographics are showing significant variation with high degree of relationship except occupation details which reveals not significant with low degree of relationship which arised on account of spread over equally to the stated different profession. Respondents found better mode of savings after joining SHGs where respondents insisted on parking savings in their SHGs, and totally rejected to park their savings with relatives / friends and neighbors. Further, they also rejected chit funds and cash in hand also found with small portion of respondents. The occupational details found to be better after joining SHGs where 23% of respondents involved in vegetable selling and substantial decrease in seasonal fruit selling.

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Table-1 : Socio economic characteristics of Respondents

Socio Economic Variable	x ²	TV @ 0.05	df	Result of x ²	"c"	Result of "c"
Marital status	193.52	7.815	3	Significant	0.81	High Degree
Age (in years)	47.90	9.488	4	Significant	0.57	High Degree
Education	19.76	7.815	3	Significant	0.53	High Degree
Occupation	4.88	11.070	5	Not Significant	0.21	Low Degree
Monthly income (INR)	35.10	9.488	4	Significant	0.50	High Degree
Living conditions	65.20	7.815	3	Significant	0.62	High Degree
Participation in social activities	81.00	3.841	1	Significant	0.67	High Degree
Training	103.47	3.841	1	Significant	0.71	High Degree
Voting and supporting a candidate in election	70.56	3.841	1	Significant	0.64	High Degree

Source: Field Survey

Note : x² = Chi-square

$$'c' = \sqrt{(x^2 / x^2 + N)}$$

Where 'c' = Contingency Co-efficient, N = Number of Observations

When the value 'c' is equal or nearer to 1, it means that there is high degree of association between attributes. Contingency co-efficient will always to be less than 1. High degree is considered here if 'c' is 0.50 and above.

Table - 2 : Occupational status and income generation before joining SHGs.

Occupation and IGAs before joining SHGs	SA	S	SWA	T
Agriculture	13	4	4	21
Petty business	8	2	2	12
Tailoring	12	2	2	16
Vegetable selling	10	3	1	14
Pickle / papad selling	9	2	3	14
Seasonal fruit selling	14	5	4	23
Total	66	18	16	100

Source : Field Survey

Hypothesis

H ₀	There exist no significant variation in the data	Reject
H ₁	There exist significant variation in the data	Accept

ANOVA Table

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F-ratio	5% F limit (From F Table)
Between the sample	266.9658	(3-1) = 2	266.9558 / 2 = 133.4829	133.4828 / 2.8942 = 46.12	
Within the sample	43.4134	(18-3) = 15	43.4134 / 15 = 2.8942		(2, 15)
Total	310.3792	(18-1) = 17			

Source : Field survey

To measure the occupational status and IGAs before joining SHGs a null hypotheses that there exists no significant variation in the data was framed. The F - ratio being 46.12 with 5% level of significance with V1 = 2 and V2 = 15.

Table - 3 : Occupational status and income generation after joining SHGs.

Occupation and IGAs after joining SHGs	SA	S	SWA	T
Agriculture	10	3	2	15
Petty business	12	2	2	16
Tailoring	9	1	1	11
Vegetable selling	14	6	3	23
Pickle / papad selling	13	2	1	16
Seasonal fruit selling	14	4	1	14
Total	72	18	10	100

Source : Field Survey

Hypothesis

H ₀	There exist no significant variation in the data	Reject
H ₁	There exist significant variation in the data	Accept

ANOVA Table

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F-ratio	5% F limit (From F Table)
Between the sample	378.95	(3-1) = 2	378.95/2 = 189.475	189.475 / 2.756 = 68.75	
Within the sample	41.3334	(18-3) = 15	41.3334/15 = 2.756		(2, 15)
Total	420.2834	(18-1) = 17			

Source : Field survey

ANOVA Analysis :

The calculated value being before 46.12 and after 68.75 and the difference being 22.63 greater than TV 3.68 @ 5% level of significance with $V_1 = 2$ and $V_2 = 15$ and hence ANOVA fails to accept H_0 and accepts H_1 and hence it is concluded that occupational status and income generating found to be better than before.

Table - 4 : Mode of savings of respondents before joining SHGs.

Mode of savings	SA	A	SWA	RT	RT ²
SHGs	0	0	0	0	0
Cash in hand	6	2	1	9	81
Bank	8	3	1	12	144
Chit Fund	25	5	2	32	1024
Post office	8	2	2	12	144
Provident fund	2	1	2	5	25
Relatives / Friends / Neighbours	24	2	1	27	729
Others	2	1	-	3	9
Total	75	16	9	100	2156

Source : Field Survey

Note : SA - Strongly Agree, A - Agree, SWA - Somewhat Agree, RT - Row Total

$$\begin{aligned} SSR &= \sum RT^2 - (RT)^2 / N \\ &= 2156 - (100)^2 / 8 = 2156 - 10000 / 8 \\ &= 2156 - 1250 = 906 \end{aligned}$$

Use the sum of squares (SSR) in the following formula to obtain Kendall's 'w'.

$$\begin{aligned} W &= 12 \times SSR / K^2 N (N^2 - 1) \\ &= 12 \times 906 / 9 \times 8 (64 - 1) = 10872 / 4536 = 2.39 \end{aligned}$$

Table - 5 : Mode of savings of respondents after joining SHGs.

Mode of savings	SA	A	SWA	RT	RT ²
SHGs	54	2	2	58	3364
Cash in hand	4	1	1	6	36
Bank	10	-	1	11	121
Chit Fund	6	1	1	8	64
Post office	3	2	1	6	36
Provident fund	3	2	1	6	36
Relatives / Friends / Neighbours	1	1	-	2	4
Others	1	1	1	3	9
Total	82	10	8	100	3670

Source : Field Survey

Note :

$$\begin{aligned} SSR &= \sum RT^2 - (RT)^2 / N \\ &= 3670 - (100)^2 / 8 = 3670 - 1250 = 2420 \end{aligned}$$

Use the sum of squares (SSR) in the following formula to obtain Kendall's 'w'.

$$\begin{aligned} W &= 12 \times SSR / K^2 N (N^2 - 1) \\ &= 12 \times 2420 / 9 \times 8 (64 - 1) = 2904 / 4536 = 6.40 \end{aligned}$$

Now find the difference between $6.40 - 2.39 = 4.01$

Test the significance of "w" by using the chi-square statistic.

$$\begin{aligned} \chi^2 &= k (n-1) w \\ &= 3 (8-1) 4.21 \\ &= 3 \times 7 \times 4.21 = 84.21 \end{aligned}$$

Decision : At 7 df (8-1) with 0.05 level of significance the TV = 14.067. The calculated value is 84.21 is higher than the critical TV and hence "w" fails to accept H_0 and accepts H_1 . Therefore it is conclude that there exists significant relationship between before and data reveals that the respondents are more aware of more of savings after joining SHGs.